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The analysis of war novel: its historical origin and narrative characteristics

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A war novel is a novel where the main plot takes place in a field of armed combat or in a home setting where the characters are preparing for war or recovering and having a post-war period. War novel is sometimes also called military fiction and uses war discourse.

The war novel's originates from the epic poetry of the classical and medieval periods, especially Homer's *The Iliad*, Virgil's *The Aeneid*, the Old English saga *Beowulf*, and the legends of King Arthur. All of these epics were oriented towards preservation of the history of conflicts between different societies, while providing an accessible narrative that could reinforce the collective memory of people.

Other important influences on the war novel includes the tragedies of such dramatists as Euripides, Seneca the Younger, Christopher Marlowe, and Shakespeare.

The war novel came of age during the nineteenth century. Works such as Stendhal's *The Charterhouse of Parma*, featuring the Battle of Waterloo and Stephen Crane's *The Red Badge of Courage* about the American Civil war established the rules and characteristics of the modern war novel as it has created contemporary war fiction discourse.

All of these works show realistic depictions of major battles, dramatic scenes of wartime horrors and atrocities, and significant insights into the nature of heroism, bravery, and morality in war.

The World War I and World War II produced an unprecedented number of war novels written by authors from countries on all sides of the conflicts. The decades following World War II period also saw the rise in significant parallel genres to the war novel.

Today war novel is represented by various literature pieces describing local armed conflicts of different scale. Many of them bring anti-war texts showing the suffering of people turned to be in the middle of the war.

War novels are divided into some types. They include the following:

Novel-event that is limited in the time and plot;

Novel-fate concerns the features of human character and outlines moral qualities of a warrior showing the origin of his heroic deeds;

Novel-life describes the life of one character focusing on his/her sufferings and biographical facts;

War educational novel presents the best human qualities and shows positive human characters. Such piece of literature can be used to educate future generations;

Novel-reflection describes internal nature of main character, his thoughts, sufferings, dreams and plans for future.

How about the narrative characteristics of war novel? War genre includes a single soldier or group of soldiers preparing for, waiting for, engaging in, and possibly recovering from wartime combat. A war novel usually have soldiers on a battlefield with the possibility of death. It's important to note that it's not every story set in a time of war. It has to build and lead to a core battle. A wartime setting could function as a background fo this genre.

A war novel is not a history lesson on war-time conflict, a bunch of battle sequences strung together, or about a protagonist who is just a bad guy. A war novel has many other characteristics.

According to Shawn Coyne, the war novel is an arch-plot genre, which has actually one hero's story or mini-plot where there are many characters. The novel culminates in the big battle event in which the combatants fight righteously and prevail or die in disgrace. War novel is also a society novel as it focuses on deeply personal and specific human conflict.

Other war novel characteristics include three types of conflict described within the plot:

External conflict which appears from fellow soldiers and/or the environmental pressures like weather, broken equipment, enemy forces, terrain, even new technologies like social networks, etc. The protagonist is motivated by the expectations and limitations of his team to stay alive, win the battle, and obtain honor via sacrificing for fellow soldiers.

An interpersonal conflict is between the opposing characters – the antagonist and the protagonist. The antagonist of a war novel is usually the enemy forces and at least one member of a soldier's own side, often a higher-ranking official. The internal conflict means the war within the protagonist and represents his/her morality trajectory. In most war novels, the conflict unfolds on one or two of these conflicts.

Other characteristics of war novel concern emotions that the author expects from the audience. The analysis of theoretical sources and war fiction shows that war genre operates several different emotions among its readers. They can be divided into two groups: excitement and fear; satisfaction, pity and contempt.

The first group – excitement and fear – means that readers choose war novel to experience courage and selflessness in the face of intense fear, without actual danger and false bravery.

The second group – satisfaction, pity and contempt – is important for readers who choose war novel to experience righteous satisfaction at the proper outcome for the protagonist, whether negative or positive. They want to feel pity for the tested and contempt for the unrepentant but righteous satisfaction when the punishment comes.

Thus, war novel is a complex linguistic phenomenon that possesses a number of narrative characteristics. Due to the importance of historical events described in such kind of fiction, war novel is highly appreciated by the readers and scholars who study war genre.